

LIPOSOMES IN COSMECEUTICALS

^{1*}Thorat Sakshi R., ²Kotkar Atiksha V., ³Fulsundar Apeksha S. and ⁴Shelke Viraj B.

^{1,2}Student of Final Year B. Pharmacy, Vidya Niketan Institute of Pharmacy and Research Center, Bota.

^{3,4}Assistant Professor, of Vidya Niketan Institute of Pharmacy and Research Center, Bota.

Article Received on 05 Nov. 2025,

Article Revised on 25 Nov. 2025,

Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17799760>

Corresponding Author*Thorat Sakshi R.**

Student of Final Year B. Pharmacy,
Vidya Niketan Institute of Pharmacy
and Research Center, Bota.

How to cite this Article: 1Thorat Sakshi R.,
2Kotkar Atiksha V., 3Fulsundar Apeksha S. and
4Shelke Viraj B.. (2025). LIPOSOMES IN
COSMECEUTICALS. World Journal of
Pharmaceutical Research, 14(23), 1637-1647.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Liposomes, spherical vesicles composed of phospholipid bilayers, are commonly used in cosmetic formulations to enhance the transport of active substances to the skin. They prevent certain hydrophilic and lipophilic substances from breaking down while also increasing their stability and availability to the body. This encapsulation enables regulated release and targeted distribution, increasing the efficacy of active substances like vitamins, peptides, and antioxidants. Liposomes are used in cosmetics to increase skin hydration, minimise indications of ageing, and promote skin barrier restoration. Advances in liposome technology, such as nanoliposomes and multilamellar liposomes, have increased their applications by facilitating greater penetration and greater release durations.^[1] Cosmeceuticals are cosmetic cosmetics combining biologically active ingredients that provide drug-like benefits. Cosmeceuticals are a rapidly increasing segment that

includes the personal care industry as well as several topical cosmetics-based therapies for treating a variety of skin disorders.^[2]

KEYWORDS: Liposomes; Encapsulation; Targeted Drug Delivery; Cosmetic.

INTRODUCTION

Liposomes, spherical vesicles made up of phospholipid bilayers, have transformed the field of cosmetic science by improving the transport and stability of active components in skincare products. Liposomes were originally designed for drug delivery in pharmaceuticals, but their

structural plasticity and biocompatibility have led to their widespread use in cosmetics today. These vesicles can encapsulate both hydrophilic and lipophilic molecules, making them suitable as carriers for a variety of active substances such as vitamins, peptides, antioxidants, and botanical extracts. The packaging technique preserves these substances against environmental degradation, such as oxidation and UV damage, extending their shelf life and effectiveness. Liposomes reflect cell membrane structures, allowing them to merge with skin cells and penetrate deeply into the skin layers than standard formulations. This property makes them very useful in skincare for targeted distribution and controlled release of active compounds, which can improve skin hydration, minimise indications of ageing, and aid in skin barrier repair. Recent advances, such as nano-liposomes and other specialised forms like ethosomes and transferosomes, have increased liposomal carriers' stability, flexibility, and penetration potency, making them more useful for skin care applications.

➤ Definition and Structure

Liposomes are spherical vesicles composed of phospholipid bilayers that can encapsulate both hydrophilic (water soluble) and hydrophobic (oil-soluble) substances. These structures are similar to cell membranes, allowing them to effectively deliver active ingredients into the deeper layers of the skin.^[3,4]

Size: Typically ranging from 50 nm to several micrometres

Composition: Composed of natural or synthetic lipids, primarily phospholipids like phosphatidylcholine.^[3,4]

Figure 1: Structure of Liposome.

Liposomes in cosmetics The term "liposome" is derived from the Greek terms "lipo" (referring to the fatty component) and "soma" (relating to the structure). Liposomes are macroscopic round vesicles made up of one or more phospholipid bilayers that are stabilised by cholesterol and have an aqueous volume surrounded entirely by a lipidic membrane. The structural similarity of the liposome bilayer to the cell membrane allows it to interact more effectively with the skin after topical administration.^[5,6] Moreover, these colloidal vesicles have the power to capture a hydrophilic or lipophilic medication, with the hydrophilic drug being trapped into the aqueous volume.

The hydrophobic chemical is captured in phospholipid bilayers, making liposomes an ideal carrier system for many kinds of pharmaceuticals, regardless of solubility. Furthermore, the biocompatibility, biodegradability, and the absence of potential tissue toxicity in comparison to the other particles carriers, Liposomes are an emerging delivering drugs carrier method in cosmeceutical applications. Figure 1 depicts the characteristic features of liposomes.^[7]

Liposomes are one of the delivery processes that aid in the absorption of cosmetic components into the skin. Liposomes also improve skin stability and hydration through surface adhesiveness, increase dermal bioavailability, and promote skin cell regeneration and targeting. In pharmaceuticals, we have a wide range of options for developing alternative dosage forms that carry the active pharmaceutical component to its site of action. However, in cosmetics, because the skin is the first line of defence against external forces and inhibits many chemicals from reaching the underlying layers or systemic circulation, there are some restrictions to delivering the active ingredient to the target site.^[8,9,10]

Liposomes play a major part in skincare enhanced delivery systems because they allow active substances to be transported into the skin without passing through the stratum corneum (the skin's outermost layer). This focused distribution guarantees that active compounds reach their designated site of action, hence increasing the overall efficacy of skincare solutions. Liposomes improve the performance of active substances by shielding them from degradation and increasing their stability. This encapsulation allows for controlled release, which ensures a long-lasting action on the skin. Features of Liposomes in Cosmetics.

Increased Hydration Mechanism: Liposomes form a protective barrier on the skin, decreasing superficial water loss (TEWL) and retaining moisture. As a result, your skin will be more hydrated and smoother.

Anti-Ageing Properties Collagen Stimulation: Liposomal delivery of antioxidants and peptides increases collagen synthesis while minimising wrinkles and fine lines.

Oxidative Stress Reduction: Liposomal delivery of antioxidants and peptides reduces fine lines and wrinkles while increasing collagen production.

Liposomes help to rebuild the skin's natural barrier, promote healing, and reduce inflammation.

UV Protection: UV filters are used for liposomes to improve stability and efficacy.^[10,11,12]

❖ Types of Cosmetic Liposomes

Cosmetic liposomes are classified into distinct categories based on their composition and indication. Depending on the features we want our beauty item to have, we can choose one of them.

➤ Transferosomes

Transferosomes are highly flexible, reactive, and efficient liposomes that have previously been used for direct transdermal medication delivery. Because of their small size (300-200 nm), they can easily penetrate the skin and cross the stratum corneum via intracellular or transcellular routes, aided by two extended flexible layers on the surface. Liposomes are made up of phospholipids and cholesterol, with added surfactants such as sodium cholate (cholic acid salt).^[13]

➤ Marinosomes

These types are made from marine lipid extracts that contain a high rate of Eicosapentaenoic acid and Docosahexaenoic acid that are omega-3 poly unsaturated fatty acids. Metabolized by the skin's epidermal enzymes, they change to their anti-inflammatory and anti-proliferative metabolites, which helps in healing many of the skin's inflammatory problems. The toxicity studies shows that this category of liposomes is safe for skin and eye contact.^[13,14]

➤ Niosome

Niosomes are small particles made of non-ionic surfactants from alkyl or di alkyl polyglycerol ethers. The usage of niosome in cosmetics and skincare is particularly beneficial since it promotes product effectiveness and penetration, increases bioavailability of poorly absorbed substances, and improves medicine stability.

Novasomes

Novasomes are non-phospholipid oligolamellar lipid vesicles of 0.1-1.0 microns. They are a type of liposome or modified.

➤ Niosome

Niosome synthesised by combining polyoxymethylene fatty acids' monoester, cholesterol, and free fatty acids at a ratio of 74/22/4. They provide additional advantages for usage in cosmetic preparations by having the ability to cleave to skin or hair shafts. This also allows for continuous release, enhancing the effectiveness and texture of these cosmetics.^[15]

➤ Ultrasomes

Ultrasomes are liposomes produced by the endonuclease isolated from *Micrococcus luteus*. They aid in the detection of ultraviolet radiation damage to the skin and can accelerate therapy by up to four times. Ultrasomes also protect the immune system by removing the harmful impact of UV radiation on DNA and reducing the release of certain cytokines such as tumour necrosis factor alpha and interleukin 1, 6, and 8, as well as minimising the risk of skin cancer.^[16]

➤ Photosome

Photosome release photolysis enzymes derived from the marine plant *Anacystinidu lans*. They are commonly found in sunscreens to prevent light from damaging the cell's DNA, hence preventing immune system suppression and lowering the chance of cancer induction.^[14]

➤ Ethosomes

Ethosomes are soft, flexible multilayer vesicles constructed from phosphatidylcholine, water, and 20-50% ethanol. Some carriers are non-invasive, allowing the component to penetrate deeply into the epidermal layer and into the systemic circulation. Etho is defined by its high ethanol percentage. Because ethanol has been shown to produce an imbalance in the arrangement of the skin's two lipid layers, it can permeate the horny layer when coupled with a vesicle.

➤ Phytosomes

Phytosomes are herbal liposomes made from phospholipids and plant extracts, including flavonoids, glycosides, and terpenoids. Phytosomes boost skin absorption of phyto molecules

and are widely utilised in cosmetics because of their high lipid profile and improved skin penetration.^[15]

➤ **Sphingosomes**

Sphingosomes are liposomes composed of ceramides that help restore dry or ageing skin by compensating for water shortage and repairing barrier function.^[13]

➤ **Nanosomes**

Nanosomes are small liposomes made of pure phosphatidylcholine with a low nanometre size range. They are used as an anti-ageing serum to boost performance and repair skin to a healthy and youthful look.^[14]

➤ **Glycerosomes**

Glycerosomes are modified liposomes that contain glycerol and phospholipids. Their unique feature is the capacity to transfer cosmeceutical active substances to the skin with excellent performance, healing, or beautifying properties. Recently, unilamellar Glycerosomes encapsulating quercetin were developed with a size of 80-110 nm, which showed improved skin kind defensive action. The future prospect is to use them for manufacturing antioxidant skin moisturisers.^[16] Oleosomes are natural liposomes that store oils, vitamins, and colours. They can be found in a number of oil-bearing plant seeds or fruits and have been demonstrated to be effective delivery mechanisms for personal care. Oleosomes derived from sea buckthorn fruit flesh exhibited high stability and antioxidant capacity.^[15] Catezome: catezome Sereno velnon-phospholipidvesi J Skin Stem Cell., 2016; 3(3): e65815. Crystal with a cationic surface charge derived from fatty acid salts of amphipathic quaternary amines.

➤ **Liposomes**

Liposomes having hydrophilic or hydrophobic cosmeceutical payloads can be maintained by hair and skin, which renders them appropriate for delivery systems where penetration is not suitable or manageable.^[15] are liposomal vesicles containing modest amounts of ethanol and terpenes or terpene combinations, which function as potent carriers with increased skin penetration abilities.

Figure 2: Various types of liposomes.

❖ Applications in Cosmetic Products:- Moisturizers

Liposomes enhance the delivery of hydrating agents, such as hyaluronic acid and glycerine, ensuring long lasting moisture retention.

Serums: High concentrations of active ingredients like vitamins C and E are encapsulated in liposomes for improved stability and penetration.

Anti-Aging Creams: Retinol and peptide-enriched formulations benefit from liposomal encapsulation, reducing irritation and enhancing effectiveness.

Sunscreens: Liposomes improve the photostability of UV filters, providing broad-spectrum protection with minimal skin irritation.^[17]

❖ CHALLENGES FACING LIPOSOMAL DRUGDELIVERY SYSTEMS

• The Reticuloendothelial System (RES) and Liposome Clearance

The RES is the primary location of liposome accumulation following systemic treatment (Poste et al., 1976; Senior, 1987). The primary organs connected with the RES include the liver, spleen, kidney, lungs, bone marrow, and lymph nodes (Senior, 1987). The liver has the greatest capability for liposomal absorption, followed by the spleen, which may store liposomes up to tenfold more than other RES organs (Chrai et al., 2002). The ability of the RES to remove liposomes from circulation is related to fenestrations in their microvasculature. Pore widths in these capillaries can range within 100 & 800 nm, which is

large enough for the most drug-loaded liposomes (50-1000 nm in size) are extravasated before being eliminated (Sapra and Allen, 2003).

Liposomes are removed in the RES by resident macrophages that interact with the phagocytic cells.^[19]

- **Opsonins and Vesicle Destabilization**

The degree of interaction between liposomal drug delivery systems and plasma proteins is critical for controlling overall nanocarrier biodistribution, potency, and toxicity (Hua and Wu, 2013). Plasma proteins have been determined to play a major part in liposomal clearance by the RES via opsonisation and vesicular destabilisation (Cullis et al., 1998). Liposome opsonisation by serum proteins is affected by several parameters, including size, surface charge, and stability (Cullis et al., 1998; Ishida et al., 2001a).

The extent of this reaction has been demonstrated to diminish with liposome size from 800 to 200 nm, as small liposomes cannot support opsonic activity (Chraietal., 2002).^[18]

- **The Accelerated Blood Clearance (ABC) Phenomenon**

Accelerated blood clearance (ABC) phenomenon:-

The interaction of liposome components with the immune system has exacerbated the challenges in translating to therapeutic applications. Synthetic alterations to improve their usability as drug delivery vehicles could trigger antibody formation against their various components and/or the encapsulated cargo. For example, repeated injections of PEGylated liposomes are associated with a loss of their long-circulating capabilities and subsequent removal from the bloodstream (Dams et al., 2000; Ishida et al., 2003, 2006b). This is known as the "accelerated blood clearance" (ABC) phenomenon.

- **Complement Activation–Related Pseudo allergy (CARPA)**

Some liposomal systems may stimulate the innate immune response, which then activates the complement system, resulting in an acute hypersensitivity syndrome known as complement activation-related pseudoallergy (CARPA). The complement system is an element of the innate immune response which is involved in many kinds of immunological and inflammatory processes (Moghimi and Hunter, 2001). A somewhat high percentage of patients (2-45%) have been documented to experience infusion-related hypersensitivity reactions to liposomal medications. In addition, CARPA has been associated with both experimental and clinically

approved liposomal formulations (e.g., Doxil R, Ambisome, and DaunoXomeR) (Szebeni, 2005; Szebeni and Moghimi, 2001). General medical treatment includes decreasing or pausing the infusion rate, as well as providing normal allergy drugs (e.g., antihistamines, epinephrine, and corticosteroids).^[20]

Figure 3: Advantages and challenges of liposome-based cosmeceutical.

CONCLUSION

Liposomes are a useful tool in the development of complicated, high-performance cosmetic formulations, providing a versatile and flexible solution to long-standing skincare difficulties. The demand for cosmeceutical products is increasing by the day, resulting in exponential expansion in the cosmeceutical market. The use of liposomes to aid in medication distribution has had a significant impact on numerous biomedical disciplines. Understanding the developments made in liposomal technology to date, along with the barriers that remain to be overcome, will enable future research to build on existing platforms while solving present translational and regulatory limitations.

REFERENCES

1. Honeywell-Nguyen PL, Bouwstra JA Vesicles as a tool for transdermal and dermal delivery. *Drug Discov Today Technol*, 2005; 2(1): 67-74.
2. Salvioni L, Morelli L, Ochoa E, Labra M, Fiandra L et al. The emerging role of nanotechnology in skincare. *Adv Coll Interface Sci.*, 2021; 293: 102437.
3. Egbaria K, Weiner N. Liposomes as a topical drug delivery system. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*, 1990; 5(3): 287-300.

4. Verma DD, Verma S, Blume G, Fahr A. Particle size of liposomes influences dermal delivery of substances into skin. *Int J Pharm.*, 2003; 258(1-2): 141-151.
5. Rahimpour Y, Hamishehkar H. Liposomes in cosmeceutics. *Expert Opin Drug Deliv*, 2012; 9: 443–455 13.
6. Lohani A, Verma A. Vesicles: potential nano carriers for the delivery of skin cosmetics. *J Cosmet Laser Ther.*, 2017; 19: 485–493.
7. de Leeuw J, de Vijlder HC, Bjerring P, Neumann HA Liposomes in dermatology today. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*, 2009; 23: 505–516 15.
8. Thakur K, Sharma G, Singh B, Chhibber S, Katare OP. Current state of nanomedicines in the treatment of topical infectious disorders. *Recent Pat Antiinfect Drug Discov*, 2018; 13: 127–150 16.
9. Carita AC, Eloy JO, Chorilli M, Lee RJ, Leonardi GR. Recent advances and perspectives in liposomes for cutaneous drug delivery. *Curr Med Chem.*, 2018; 25: 606–635.
10. Kirjavainen M, Urtti A, Valjakka-Koskela R, Kiesvaara J, Mönkkönen J. Liposome-skin interactions and their effects on the skin permeation of drugs. *Eur J Pharm Sci.*, 1999; 7(4): 279-286.
11. Cevc G. Lipid vesicles and other colloids as drug carriers on the skin. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*, 2004; 56(5): 675-711.
12. Elsayed MM, Abdallah OY, Naggar VF, Khalafallah NM. Lipid vesicles for skin delivery of drugs: Reviewing three decades of research. *Int J Pharm.*, 2007; 332(1,2): 1-16.
13. Reva T, Vaseem AA, Satyaprakash S, Md.khalid JA. Liposomes: The novel approach in cosmaceuticals. *World J Pharm Pharm Sci.*, 2015; 4(6): 1616–40.
14. Socaciu C. New technologies to synthesize. Extract and encapsulate natural food colorants. *Bull Univ Agric Sci Vet Med Cluj-Napoca Animal Sci Biotechnol*, 2009; 64(1-2).
15. NounouMI, El-KhordaguiLK, KhalafallahNA, KhalilSA. Liposomal for mulation for dermal and transdermal drug delivery: past, present and future. *Recent Pat Drug Deliv Formul*, 2008; 2(1): 9–18. [PubMed: 19075893].
16. Lakshmi PK, Kalpana B, Prasanthi D. Invasomes-novel Vesicular Carriers for Enhanced Skin Permeation. *System Rev Pharm.*, 2013; 4(1): 26. doi:10.4103/0975- 8453.135837.
17. Liu W, Hu M, Liu W. Applications of liposomes in cosmetics. *Asian J Pharm Sci.*, 2013; 8(4): 219-227.
18. El Maghraby GM, Barry BW, Williams AC. Liposomes and skin: From drug delivery to model membranes. *Eur J Pharm Sci.*, 2008; 34(4-5): 203-222.

19. Guo, X., and Szoka, F. C. Jr. Chemical approaches to triggerable lipid vesicles for drug and gene delivery. *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2003; 36: 335–341. doi: 10.1021/ar9703241
20. Koning, G. A., and Storm, G. Targeted drug delivery systems for the intracellular delivery of macromolecular drugs. *Drug Discov. Today*, 2003; 8: 482–483. doi: 10.1016/S1359-6446(03)02699-0
21. Bendas, G. Immunoliposomes: a promising approach to targeting cancer therapy. *BioDrugs*, 2001; 15: 215–224. doi: 10.2165/00063030-200115040-00002
22. Bibi, S., Lattmann, E., Mohammed, A. R., and Perrie, Y. Trigger release liposome systems: local and remote controlled delivery? *J. Microencapsul*, 2012; 29: 262–276. doi: 10.3109/02652048.2011.646330